

Studies of the Hydrolysis of Esters in Aqueous Glycol

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Research on the effect of the medium on the kinetic characteristics is important in elucidating the mechanism of reactions in liquid phase¹. Variation in the solvent properties such as dielectric constant and viscosity together with variation in the reagent concentration and temperature, make it possible to obtain the required information regarding the mechanism of the chemical reaction. The liquid phase reaction is usually a multistage process including two to three or more simple stages. The physical models used to make quantitative allowance for the effect of medium on the rate of liquid phase reaction involve ion-dipole interactions in terms of solvation and solute-solvent interactions. The survey of the literature testifies that no study of the hydrolysis of the esters in the highly viscous solvents like glycols has been carried out so far. In the present communication, the results on acid hydrolysis of methyl and ethyl acetate in aqueous glycols (EG and DEG) are reported.

Results and Discussion

The hydrolysis of an ester with an acidic solution is a pseudo-first order reaction. In terms of the experimentally measurable parameters, the rate equation for the hydrolysis is written as

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \left(\frac{V_{\infty} - V_0}{V_{\infty} - V_t} \right) \quad (1)$$

where k is the rate constant of the reaction, V_0 the volume of the alkali used at the start of the reaction, V_t and V_{∞} are the volumes of alkali used respectively at time t and at infinite time, i.e. when reaction is complete. According to the expression (1), the plot of $\log(V_{\infty} - V_t)$ vs t should give a straight line. In the present investigation, straight line is obtained in all the solvent media and at all the temperatures. The values of k is estimated from the slopes ($k/2.303$) and are given in Tables 1 and 2.

The quantitative allowance for the effect of the medium on the rate constant of the elementary reaction consists in obtaining the function,

$$k = f(a, b, c, \dots, p, q, r) \quad (2)$$

where a, b, c are the parameters characterising the properties of the reagents and p, q, r the parameters

characterising the properties of the medium. The effect of the viscosity and dielectric constant is shown in Fig. 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF METHYL ACETATE AND ETHYL ACETATE IN ETHYLENEGLYCOL-WATER AND DIETHYLENEGLYCOL-WATER MIXTURES AT 25°C*

Solvent composition % (w/w)	10 ⁴ k (min ⁻¹)	
	EG-H ₂ O system	DEG-H ₂ O system
0	6.35 (7.51)	6.35 (7.51)
20	9.30 (8.60)	7.90 (8.31)
40	11.50 (9.85)	11.45 (8.91)
60	14.40 (12.10)	12.30 (10.95)
80	15.80 (26.00)	13.85 (13.35)

*Values in parenthesis corresponds to ethylacetate.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF METHYL ACETATE AND ETHYL ACETATE IN 50% ETHYLENEGLYCOL AND 50% DIETHYLENEGLYCOL AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES*

Temp. °C	10 ⁴ k (min ⁻¹)	
	EG-H ₂ O system	DEG-H ₂ O system
25	12.5 (11.8)	11.2 (10.5)
30	18.9 (20.3)	14.1 (13.0)
35	26.0 (31.0)	24.4 (22.7)

*Values in parenthesis corresponds to ethylacetate.

Fig. 1. Variation of rate constant versus viscosity and dielectric constant: (O) methyl acetate and (Δ) ethyl acetate in ethylene glycol-water system.

The Fig. 1 shows that the rate constant increases with the increase in viscosity and with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium. All the existing attempts to allow for the effect of the medium on the rate of the reaction are based on the following assumptions: (i) the presence of an equilibrium (chemical, diffusional or statistical) between the initial reacting particles A and B and also with some 'formation' and (2) on the presence of a proportional law between the rate of appearance of the final product and the concentration of this 'formation'. It is assumed^{2,3} that the elementary reaction consists of two 'sub-elementary' stages: (I) $A+B \rightleftharpoons X$, and (II) $X \rightarrow AB$.

The true nature of the intermediate formation and the final results always depends on whether X is a physical or chemical formation. If it is considered that the reaction involves the combination of two ions to form an activated complex (chemical formation or physical formation), the effect of medium on the rate constant (k) can be explained by the consideration of the following two physical models^{3,4}.

(A) Let us consider that ions involved in the reaction are point charges, $Z_i e$, which approach each other from infinity to a distance R_{AB} . Assuming medium as a continuous structureless dielectric (continuum) with a static dielectric constant, the charges will distribute in the activated complex and the charges remain separated and one gets,

$$-2.303k/T \frac{\delta(\log k)}{\delta(1/\epsilon)} = \frac{Z_A Z_B e^2}{R_{AB}} \quad (3)$$

where k' is the Boltzman constant, k the rate constant, ϵ the dielectric constant of the medium, Z_A and Z_B are the charges of ions A and B, and e is the electronic charge, $R_{AB} = r_A + r_B$, where r_A and r_B are the radii of the ions.

According to equation (3), the plot of $\log k$ vs $1/\epsilon$ will be a straight line and it has been found so. The plots therefore suggest that the initial reagents and the activated complex are similar to one another.

(B) Let us consider that the ions are rigid conducting spheres with radii r_A and r_B and the charges $Z_A e$ and $Z_B e$ are concentrated at one point on the sphere surface constituting the ion. When the spheres interact, they form a new sphere of radius r_x with charge $(Z_A + Z_B)e$, considering medium as continuum with a static dielectric constant. The consideration of it gives the following relation between k and ϵ ,

$$\begin{aligned} & -2.303 k T \frac{\delta(\log k)}{\delta(1/\epsilon)} \\ & = \frac{e^2}{2} \left[\frac{(Z_A + Z_B)^2}{r_x} - \frac{Z_A^2}{r_A} - \frac{Z_B^2}{r_B} \right] \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

According to expression (4), the plot of $\log k$ vs $1/\epsilon$ is again a straight line but the slope differs for

both the models. The difference in slopes may be attributed to the formation of the diffusion pair in case of model represented by expression (4) and the formation of activated complex in case of model represented by the expression (3). Further, the values of the slope is 62.92 in case of EG and 28.22 in case of DEG. This may be attributed to the greater solvation of ionic species in case of diethyleneglycol making R_{AB} values larger than in ethyleneglycol.

Effect of temperature on the rate constant: The activation energy for the hydrolysis of methyl acetate and ethyl acetate in 50% EG and 50% DEG has been estimated⁵ from the linear plots of $\log k$ vs $1/T$, and the values are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF ACTIVATION ENERGY FOR DIFFERENT SYSTEMS

System	Activation energy 10^{-3} (J mol ⁻¹)
Methyl acetate in 50% EG	8.66
Methyl acetate in 50% DEG	12.95
Ethyl acetate in 50% EG	9.03
Ethyl acetate in 50% DEG	14.71

Table 3 shows that the activation energy is higher in case of diethyleneglycol and it may be attributed to the more viscous nature of the diethyleneglycol and to the greater solvation⁶ of the reacting species in diethyleneglycol than in ethyleneglycol.

Experimental

Ethyleneglycol and diethyleneglycol were used after purification as described earlier^{6,7}. Water of specific conductance of the order of $10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ was used for preparing aqueous mixtures of EG and DEG. HCl (AnalaR) was used for generating HCl-gas for making acidic solutions of glycols for hydrolysis. Methyl acetate of pure grade was purified as described elsewhere⁸.

Preparation of solution: The aqueous solutions of EG and DEG were prepared by weight. The acidic solutions of aqueous glycols were prepared as follows. HCl gas was obtained by pouring dropwise the hydrochloric acid over sulphuric acid, which was made to pass through sulphuric acid to make it moisture-free. This gas was then dissolved in various aqueous glycol mixtures. The acid solution thus prepared was standardised to 0.5 N acid by titrating it against standard alkaline solution.

The procedure followed for the study was the same as described elsewhere⁹. All experiments were carried out in a constant-temperature bath ($\pm 0.05^\circ$).

NOTES

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